

Notes

Spectrophotometric studies of V(IV) 4-Hydroxy 3-formylazobenzene and Mg(II) and Ni(II) Sodium 4-Hydroxy 3-formylazobenzene 4'-Sulphonate Complexes

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Manuscript received 18 September 1972; revised 22 February 1973; accepted 15 February 1974

IN continuation of our previous communication¹⁷ we now report the spectrophotometric studies of the complexes of V(IV) with 4-hydroxy 3-formylazobenzene (HFB) and Ni(II) and Mg(II) with sodium 4-hydroxy 3-formylazobenzene 4'-sulphonate (SHFBS).

The synthesis of the ligand and their properties have been described in the previous communication¹.

A Hilger and Watts (England) spectrophotometer was used for absorption measurements.

The studies with SHFBS were carried out in aqueous medium while those with HFB in 42% (V/V) alcohol-water mixture.

The λ_{max} of the HFB was found at 430 nm while that of the V(IV) complex was found at 470 nm (at pH 5 to 6) and of SHFBS was found at 590 nm and Mg(II) and Ni(II) complexes were found at 530 nm (at pH 6.0 to 8.0). Hence these wave lengths were chosen to study stoichiometry of the components by Job's continuous variation, mole ratio and slope ratio methods. The validity of Beer's law was seen. The absorbance measurements were carried out after 24 hrs of equilibration. The colour did not fade even after one week. The pH of the solutions were adjusted at the required level by using different buffer solutions. The absorbance measurements were carried out between 350 to 950 nm at 30°.

In order to derive the composition of the complex the following methods were used :

- 1) Job's method² using equimolar metal and ligand solutions ;
- 2) Mole Ratio Method³ ;
- 3) Slope Ratio Method⁴.

All the solutions were adjusted to the same solvent composition in the case of the V(IV)-HFB complex.

The stability constants were calculated from the absorbance data using the mole ratio method.

The values of 'a' for V(IV)-HFB, Mg(II)-SHFBS and Ni(II)-SHFBS complexes were calculated to be 0.061, 0.34 and 0.35 respectively using the above values of 'a' and instability and the stability constants have been calculated.

The standard free energy of formation of the complexes have been calculated using the relation $\Delta F = -RT \ln K$.

V(IV), Mg(II) and Ni(II) were found to form 1:2 complexes. The log K values for the V(IV)-HFB, Mg(II)-SHFBS and Ni(II)-SHFBS chelates were calculated to be 8.4352, 6.0207 and 5.9767 respectively.

The ΔF values for these complexes were found to be -11.7722, -8.4026 and -8.3393 K.Cals/mole respectively at 30°.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their thanks to Prof. R. C. Kapoor, Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur for providing laboratory facilities and to the University authorities for awarding a research scholarship to one of us (P.N.M.D.).

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Studies on the Clay Mineralogy of Aligarh Soil Profiles

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Manuscript received 30 May 1973; revised 12 December 1973; accepted 15 February 1974

ALIGARH district (latitude 28° north and 78° east) is an important soil area among the districts of Uttar Pradesh. It has large tracts of alkaline

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